

NASA Science Mission Directorate Transform to Open Science (TOPS) **Community Panel Summary Report: June 2023**

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY:

As a driver of scientific progress and societal impact, open science—the practice of making research, data, and methodologies freely accessible to the public, fostering transparency and innovation on a global scale—has the potential to revolutionize the scientific landscape, accelerate discoveries, and encourage cooperation. At a time of significant interconnectedness and complex global challenges, knowledge sharing, cooperation, and innovation are vital.

NASA is committed to advancing open science and building a more inclusive and accessible scientific community, through the Open-Source Science Initiative ([OSSSI](#)). Since 2023 is “A Year of Open Science” - as declared by NASA, the [White House](#) and other [Federal Agencies](#), OSSSI continues to support the goals and priorities of the Transform to Open Science ([TOPS](#)) mission. TOPS is a five-year program that seeks to increase the reach and visibility of open science projects, curate and share open science tools and resources, and create additional opportunities for communities to engage in open science.

The [TOPS Community Panel](#) reviews strategies and provides input on NASA’s plans for transitioning to open-source science. A diverse group of scholars and practitioners from various academic disciplines and research areas, panelists share their expertise and offer feedback on TOPS’ mission and activities. This report contains a summary of presentations from the third meeting of the TOPS Community Panel where the assembled group shared their views on an emerging open science curriculum, training twenty thousand scientists, and doubling participation in open science events from underserved communities. TOPS, TOPS partners, panelists, and the greater NASA scientific community also offered feedback on strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats regarding the presented information. All input will be used to improve TOPS plans, bolster community engagement, and support overall missions and goals.

PANELISTS:

Justin Ballenger, James Colliander, Monica Granados, Pen-Yuan Hsing, SherAaron Hurt, Logan Kilpatrick, Brian Nosek, Fernando Perez, Malvika Sharan, Qiusheng Wu

PANEL INFORMATION: [AGENDA](#)

DAY 1: TOPS UPDATE AND CREATING THE CURRICULUM

Links to [slides](#), [video recording](#), [transcription](#).

DAY 2: TRAINING 20K SCIENTISTS

Links to [slides](#), [video recording](#), [transcription](#).

DAY 3: DOUBLING PARTICIPATION

Links to [slides](#), [video recording](#), [transcription](#).

Summary: [PDFs](#) of all slides, all days.

ATTENDANCE:

DAY 1: 141 PARTICIPANTS

DAY 2: 105 PARTICIPANTS

DAY 3: 81 PARTICIPANTS

1) KEY DELIVERABLES - SUMMARY OF PROJECT AND RESULTS (~1 PAGE)

- a) Review high-level updates on the TOPS program and the creation of an open-source science curriculum.
- b) Examine the effectiveness of TOPS priorities for advancing project goals.
- c) Consider outreach and engagement strategies for underserved communities to promote inclusion and encourage a sense of belonging in TOPS initiatives.

2) DAY 1: TOPS UPDATE AND CREATING THE CURRICULUM (SUMMARY: MALCOLM GLOVER, EDITORS: HOLLY NORTON AND CHELLE GENTEMANN, REVIEW: YVONNE IVEY-PARKER, QIUSHENG WU, SHERAARON HURT) (~4 PAGES)

TOPS is a NASA-funded open-source science initiative to make science more accessible, reproducible, and inclusive. NASA recognizes that open-source science is of paramount importance in driving scientific progress, aiding technological advancements, and addressing global challenges. Day One of the TOPS Community Panel Symposium highlighted the status of various TOPS initiatives and explored the process of creating the open-source science curriculum. The day began with an overview of the three-day event and a review of the Community Panel's code of conduct, by Holly Norton, TOPS Content Coordinator. Welcome remarks from TOPS Science Lead Chelle Gentemann were extended to all participants.

During the first half of the meeting, Kevin Murphy, NASA's Chief Science Data Officer, welcomed attendees and offered detailed information on the Science Mission Directorate (SMD) strategy for data management and computing for groundbreaking

science, the OSTP memorandum on ensuring free, immediate, and equitable access to federally funded research, and the scientific information policy for the Science Mission Directorate: SDP-41a. Murphy shared that the Chief Science Data Office (CSDO) within the Science Mission Directorate is responsible for implementing the capabilities to achieve the activities outlined in the aforementioned documents. In the same vein, the CSDO has three important goals:

1. Goal One: Develop and Implement Capabilities to Enable Open Science
2. Goal Two: Continuous Evolution of Data and Computing Systems
3. Goal Three: Harness the Community and Strategic Partnerships for Innovation

Murphy made clear that NASA's approach for putting open science into practice is straightforward. "We see science as an active, participatory endeavor, and being able to work with and collaborate with people both internal to NASA, but also, more importantly, external to NASA is critically important," said Murphy. To support this view, NASA Science dedicated funding and strategic support to establish the [Open-Source Science Initiative](#). This initiative is built on four pillars that collaborate and enrich one another, to enable open science across all of our scientific communities. The pillars are:

1. Policy and Governance: Implement policies that advance open science, support SMD working groups and meetings, and develop standards and governance.
2. Core Data and Computing Services: Develop SMD-wide data and computing infrastructure (Cloud and HEC), provide tools for the discovery of NASA's scientific information, reduce the burden of SPD-41a, and support the adoption of advanced technologies (AI/ML).
3. Open Science Incentives: Grants, prizes, and challenges to enable groundbreaking scientific discoveries using open science principles and tools.
4. Community Engagement: Advance open science practices in the SMD community and build strategic partnerships for innovation in open science.

Murphy's remarks concluded with a review of SPD-41a, NASA's Science Mission Directorate's updated Scientific Information Policy, as well as an overview of the Core Data and Computing Services Program and a summary of NASA open-source science funding priorities. Later, Chelle Gentemann, the TOPS Science Lead, provided an update on the TOPS program. Gentemann explained how TOPS is focused on supporting science communities in the transition to open science by developing interagency, international and external collaborations around open science, and advancing broader participation in science. The TOPS team is responsible for the programmatic design, concept development, strategic vision and overall reporting to the Chief Science Data Office. The TOPS initiative is composed of many efforts and includes a variety of stakeholders from both within and outside of NASA. In order to streamline and organize these efforts and stakeholders, the TOPS Project Office (PO) was created to:

1. Train 20,000 scientists

2. Increase Open Science visibility
3. Measure the performance of TOPS
4. Coordinate TOPS activities

According to Gentemann, the TOPS vision is a future where “new scientific discoveries and solutions are enabled by inclusive open science collaborations.” The initiative’s mission is to inspire and empower scientists, researchers and communities to embrace open science as a catalyst for positive change, leading to a more equitable and impactful scientific ecosystem.” As shared with the assembled group, NASA’s TOPS program is a 5-year initiative designed to accelerate scientific discovery by accelerating the adoption of open science through helping 20,000 scientists earn open science badges, having two times the participation of underrepresented communities in TOPS activities, and enable 5 major scientific discoveries based in open science practices. Gentemann’s remarks also included a review of the TOPS initiative’s community engagement strategy, details on how members of the public can earn a NASA open science certification, and information on the CERN-NASA Open Science Summit in Geneva, Switzerland.

Later, Jamaica Jones, the Transform to Open Science Interagency Coordination Lead, shared additional information on her work with Gentemann on NASA’s *Year of Open Science initiative* and the collaborative efforts of federal agencies. Jones mentioned the White House Office of Science and Technology Policy (OSTP) is part of the White House Science and Technology Advisory structure, working as part of the National Science and Technology Council (NSTC) and in concert with the President’s Council of Advisors on Science and Technology (PCAST). Within this structure, the NSTC Subcommittee on Open Science (SOS) meets monthly convening over 40 agency representatives in discussion and advancement of open science principles and practices. SOS comprises multiple subgroups, including those exploring open science infrastructure, effective data management, and Year of Open Science efforts.

Jones also provided an update on the work of the SOS Subgroup on a Year of Open Science, which is often referred to as SYOS. The Subgroup is co-chaired by NASA, NSF and NOAA and includes 16 participating federal agencies that together represent over 90 billion dollars in federal science funding. SYOS was formed in May 2022 and after securing the formal White House recognition of 2023 as a Year of Open Science the subgroup has also drafted four goals for a Year of Open Science. These include:

1. Establishing strategic approaches for advancing open science
2. Engaging underrepresented communities in open science and research
3. Incentivizing open science activities in reviews and recognition, and
4. Increasing openness and transparency in review processes

These goals were drafted to help guide agencies in implementing open science practices and policies across their broader communities. The presentation concluded with a review of the 2023 Year of Open Science agency activities and accomplishments, as well

as a conversation about how NASA and the TOPS and OSSI teams are working to strategically align planning and programming with the four goals of a Year of Open Science. Later in the day, Diana Ly, the OS101 Project Manager, shared an update on the work of the Science 101 Curriculum and Development team based out of the Ames Research Center in Silicon Valley. The Ames team was tasked with the responsibility of coordinating the development of OS101 curricula – both the instructor-led training as well as the development of the Massive Online Open Course (MOOC). Ly's remarks included detailed descriptions of the five modules that make up the OS101 curriculum.

The Ames curriculum team encourages interested parties to take the first module, titled "Ethos of Open Science," with the support of an instructor. The other four modules can be taken as an instructor-led training (ILT) or completed via the MOOC. There will be micro-badges given to participants as they complete each module and they can earn a TOPS Open Science badge after they complete all five modules. MOOC developers are working closely with other NASA officials to have both the ILT and e-learning courses available for community review. MOOC developer and Chief Learning Officer Ilona Serrao shared with attendees the status of those efforts. Day One ended with TOPS Community Panelists sharing their ideas on how to improve module content.

3) DAY 2: TRAINING 20K SCIENTISTS (SUMMARY: MALCOLM GLOVER, EDITORS: HOLLY NORTON AND CHELLE GENTEMANN, REVIEW: YVONNE IVEY-PARKER, QIUSHENG WU, SHERAARON HURT) (~2 PAGES)

Day Two of the TOPS Community Panel Symposium covered a series of efforts underway to help ensure 20K scientists are trained via the TOPS curriculum. The day's sessions began with welcome remarks from Chelle Gentemann, TOPS Science Lead, and introductory remarks, as well as a review of the Community Panel's code of conduct, by Holly Norton, TOPS Content Coordinator. Following these opening comments, Kylie Wang, a representative from NASA Research and Education Support Services (NRESS), talked with TOPS Community Panelists about NASA's process for generating honoraria.

After a brief break, summit participants received updates on the Transform to Open Science Training (TOPST) Program. TOPST Program Officer Steve Crawford said the program's objectives are to advance open science literacy for all who do research relevant to NASA's Science Mission Directorate (SMD) through training and workshops, targeting audiences from undergraduate students to established scientists and managers. Proposals were solicited for the following activities supported under this element:

- The development of ScienceCore, a discipline specific scientific use cases curriculum,
- Implementation of Summer Schools to teach OpenCore, and
- Implementation of Virtual Cohorts to help complete OpenCore

Crawford shared additional details on the proposal submission and review process, as well as the primary focus of ScienceCore, the design of Summer Schools, and the

priorities of Virtual Cohorts. After a brief session break, OS101 Project Manager Diana Ly unveiled preliminary designs for Open Science 101 badges. The OS101 team will be working with [Credly](#) for NASA TOPS Open Science badging. In terms of OS101 Instructor Training, Ly noted NASA-funded teams had potential instructors go through the [Carpentries](#) instructor training workshop to improve teaching skills. Two workshops, specifically for OS101 trainers, were held in May and future training workshops will be integrated with other Carpentries instructor workshops. Instructor workshops through the Carpentries have the following goals:

- Introduce you to evidence-based teaching practices.
- Teach you how to create a positive environment for learners at your workshops.
- Provide opportunities for you to practice and build your teaching skills.
- Help you become integrated into the Carpentries community.
- Prepare you to use these teaching skills in teaching [Carpentries workshops](#).

After completing the Carpentries instructor training, instructors must follow up with the OS101 content training workshop to be OS101 certified. Later, MOOC developer and Chief Learning Officer Ilona Serrao talked with members of the Community Panel about the learning ecosystem that defines the five open science modules. Panelists gave their suggestions for improving the design, content, and overall approach of the MOOC. At the conclusion of this discussion, Amanda Adams, a Communications Lead who works on the TOPS team at the Marshall Space Flight Center, fielded questions about the TOPS initiative from panelists and the broader audience during the Community Forum portion of the event. Day Two concluded with Paul Bremner, a Project Scientist at the Marshall Space Flight Center, sharing updates on goals for: promoting and offering open science learning to the public in 2023, completing the testing of the MOOC-only curriculum, ensuring TOPST reaches large and diverse audiences, and preparing for efforts in 2024 that will help ensure NASA is on track to meet the goal of training 20K scientists.

4) DAY 3: DOUBLING PARTICIPATION (SUMMARY: MALCOLM GLOVER, EDITORS: HOLLY NORTON AND CHELLE GENTEMANN, REVIEW: YVONNE IVEY-PARKER, QIUSHENG WU, SHERAARON HURT) (~7 PAGES)

Day three began with Holly Norton, the TOPS Content Coordinator, welcoming the panel and audience, as well as outlining the day's events. After those opening remarks, Amanda Adams, a Communications Lead at the Marshall Space Flight Center, shared details on the work of the TOPS Communications Team and their recruitment and outreach strategy. The TOPS team is targeting the general scientific community as well as focusing on underserved groups, with a priority audience of anyone that could, or does, receive NASA SMD funding for science activities. During a conversation about the TOPS Engagement Strategy for 2024, Paul Bremner, a Project Scientist at the Marshall Space Flight Center, described NASA's commitment to building on existing relationships and boosting support for TOPS at conferences and minority-serving institutions.

During a conversation about NASA's diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility (DEIA) engagement strategy, TOPS Community Coordinator Malcolm Glover reiterated the agency's commitment to DEIA. NASA is dedicated to:

- Promoting an environment where people consistently and systematically receive fair, just, and impartial treatment;
- Fostering a culture in which people feel welcomed, respected, included, and engaged; and
- Ensuring people can fully and independently access facilities, information and communication technology, programs, and services

Creating a sense of belonging will be a crucial component of ensuring members of underserved communities feel seen, heard, and valued in every aspect of the TOPS initiative. Glover noted belonging is the feeling of being accepted by others as your authentic self and he said it is an important part of efforts to create and sustain an inclusive culture at NASA. True belonging in any organization means people feel:

- Valued because of their lived experiences;
- Seen for their unique contributions;
- Heard when they share insights;
- Connected to their team members;
- Supported in their work and career development; and
- Proud of their organization's values and purpose

After exploring some of the select components of belonging with panel participants, Glover updated attendees on the Minority University Research and Education Project (MUREP) that provides financial assistance via competitive awards to Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs), including Historically Black Colleges and Universities. He also shared information on the new Data Science Equity, Access, and Priority in Research and Education (DEAP) opportunity. NASA awarded \$11.7 million to eight HBCUs through DEAP. These awards support efforts by HBCU students and faculty to conduct data science research that will contribute to NASA's mission. Glover concluded his remarks with a discussion about items within Goal Two of the "A Year of Open Science Tentative Plan." Community panel members and other attendees shared their thoughts and ideas on how TOPS can engage underrepresented communities in open science and research.

The events of Day Three ended with TOPS Content Coordinator Holly Norton leading a SWOT analysis activity. For the remainder of the day, panelists shared their perspectives on the strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with various TOPS priorities. Details from this discussion are listed below:

Panelist Feedback for the Three-day event:

Strengths:

1. The development of the TOPS team is impressive. Personnel are prepared to help advance the mission.

2. There is a momentum that is pushing toward open science and increased participation from a year ago. TOPS is finding ways to include more people, educate diverse groups of people, and make sure its initiatives aid scientific research and study.
3. This initiative continues to be a collaborative endeavor with support from experts in government, the sciences, facilitation, curriculum development, and community engagement. TOPS should continue to cooperate across agencies and sectors to make this effort sustainable and successful.
4. The power of the NASA brand/name makes people want to be a part of the TOPS initiative, organize around open science principles, and work collectively to draw others around the world to these open science efforts. People will look to NASA for leadership. In the global community, people want to be a part of these collaborative efforts. Moreover, the community forum and panels are powerful and have a lot of potential.
5. Members of the Community Panel see the TOPS team hearing and implementing their recommendations. The work of TOPS is public, transparent, and inspiring. Having hard conversations in public is important. TOPS is considering diversity, equity and inclusion in a lot of dimensions. Continue taking steps toward lingual diversity in this open science work.
6. TOPS is moving the market and the needle in efforts to advance open science. The vision of the team is putting in action what is necessary to engage with the community in meaningful ways with both openness and responsiveness. This work is making an impact.
7. The TOPS Team has a “strategic vision.” The team is willing to think big and systemically which takes courage and team members are good at thinking strategically and executing well.

Weaknesses:

1. There are technical concerns. It remains unclear whether there will be a continual flow from the content development of a course to the final product of what students/learners see. There may be instances where modules need to be beta-tested and reviewed to ensure the material works and make sure it is adaptable and accessible. Make sure the technical learning is as frictionless as possible.
2. NASA does not have a long history of engaging in efforts aimed at encouraging people to change set behaviors, especially when it comes to influencing people to share information. The TOPS team needs to (1) set some milestones and touchpoints to determine in Year Two whether this effort at “social engineering” within NASA is actually working. (2) The learners being imagined as participants in a MOOC are traditional undergraduate students, but the team should be thinking about early career professionals.

3. With a different participant/learner pool, the MOOC may not be the best tool. Remember to meet the learners where they are doing the work and then use the right tool to reach them.
4. NASA and the TOPS team must remember the process of Open Science is collaborative and not necessarily PowerPoint slide-based. People want to participate. Develop processes that support engagement. Remember, people want to write and direct the movie... they don't want to just watch it.
5. More information should be captured about the entirety of this process. Make sure to have ethnographers and other scholars on the team who can bring social sciences expertise to this work and catalog the history of what is being done and accomplished.
6. There is so much going on with these TOPS endeavors that it may be hard to keep track of everything that is happening. Keep it simple. For instance, researchers, librarians, etc. should be able to go to the website and know exactly how they can get involved with various TOPS activities and access materials that meet their diverse needs. Here is an example: <https://openclimatecampaign.org/get-involved/>
7. There needs to be a central location for the TOPS website. Possibly a site or tool that allows you to add members so that you can have future ambassadors for the program. Have different resources for different groups. Customize the offerings: researchers, students, educators, etc.

Opportunities:

1. TOPS should connect with universities and local communities to push TOPS efforts forward. There is only so much the federal government can do to ensure the success of this initiative.
2. Project-based learning can contextualize what open science means to people. This can be created by generating projects around the NASA TOPS mission and this would be transformational in addition to the MOOC.
3. Consider how the work of TOPS and other OSSI initiatives integrate with the Artemis mission and various NASA projects that aid citizen science and encourage youth activities.
4. Incentivize researchers, everyone who completes a Year of Open Science modules can be a part of some big write-up of the outcomes of this initiative. Find ways to encourage completion of course content.
5. Engage young people in these efforts. Consider collaborations with the International Science and Engineering Fair. NASA can sponsor a prize at Science Fairs to get young people interested in open science.
6. There should be more direct engagement with specific open-source teams and communities. Consider scientific Python Batch Processing projects. There should

also be more direct engagement and support from NASA at [JupyterCon](#) and other conferences.

7. Think about how NASA can help move the needle on working with industry to engage in open science. Create a culture where the industry can sustain an open science ecosystem rather than just being a temporary source of support to achieve a NASA goal.
8. Engage Hispanic-serving institutions.
9. Academic incentives and engagement with early career professionals need to happen. Work with deans, department chairs, and formal academic structures to make that happen.
10. Structure the MOOC in a way that is also relevant to K-12 students to encourage continued learning among students possibly in AP courses, summer learning programs, and beyond.
11. NASA should start vetting external open science projects and get industry and other institutions to embed best practices. NASA should lead the way in building learning ecosystems of open science.
12. The TOPS Community Panel is building valuable skills in their communities and with their learners.
13. TOPS should continue the work of building the professional skills of community leaders and helping students understand that open science is filled with transferable skills.
14. Focus on the strengths that learners from diverse communities bring to the classroom and the practice of teaching open science.
15. NASA TOPS should find ways to make sure learners and teachers of the open science curriculum have opportunities to connect, collaborate and share the best practices they are using no matter where they live in the world.

Threats:

1. There seems to be a shift in the target audience for the learning modules. TOPS may need to take more of a targeted approach to outreach and engagement to ensure it is meeting the needs of various stakeholders.
2. Remember, research and operations within NASA are inextricably linked and sometimes there are individuals and processes that try to separate the two. There is an opportunity to celebrate open science as a pathway to yield benefits.
3. Sustainability of these ideas is a threat. From funding to finding concrete ways to advance these efforts. Consider if there is a change in public policy or in political leadership and how that could impact this program.

4. If an early career researcher gets scooped, there could be a problem for TOPS. How do you handle perceived drawbacks to open science? Come up with best practices for shared credit and attribution.
5. Consider how hostile governments might use open science data to advance their nefarious purposes.
6. The TOPS team must consider that openness may be perceived as a risk by some in the government who recognize that there may be a hostile power that views open access to information as a weakness.
7. Accessibility matters. Both the TOPS Community Panel and NASA needs to think about what they can do at local institutions and within the agency to make sure materials and tools are open and accessible to everyone.
8. The 20k goal is important. TOPS may need to offer incentives to encourage people to complete the modules to help NASA reach that 20k goal. TOPS may want to create a campaign online or a tracker that people can view to “join the movement” to help NASA meet the 20K goal and see the progress of that effort.

Engagement Strategies Feedback:

1. What are the plans for engaging with the Global South communities? Consider how the DEIA matrix can be advanced in a global context.
2. Engagement can be holding a common space with international groups and creating space for global conversations on open science that can stimulate connection, promote collaboration, and advance open science best practices.
3. Don't underestimate the weight that NASA carries. The prestige of NASA and the value of what TOPS is doing can have a big impact.
4. Recognize that the NASA name matters in diverse communities around the world. TOPS has “convening power” and different stakeholder groups and entities in communities across the globe will listen when there is an opportunity to collaborate with or support a NASA mission.
5. Inclusive language matters. Be sure documents and information have generic terms that can be easily understood by diverse audiences. For instance, Research 1 (R1) universities, federal agencies, etc. are terms that are not used in other countries.
6. Find ways to share the open science highlights that different federal agencies are doing throughout a Year of Open Science. Highlight some of the key achievements of those agencies to advance the cause.
7. Stick to the TOPS strategy because it was developed in an intentional way. There can be small changes made if those changes help the team reach its goals at the end of the 5-year mission.

8. Recognize that there are groups that may not have the capacity to train researchers but if they know about the TOPS curriculum they can send researchers your way for additional training.

5) [CREDIT AUTHOR STATEMENT](#)

Please note the section (last name and what you worked on (original text, edits, figures, comments, organization...). Eg. Day 1: Perez, Sharan, Hightower, original text. Wu, Woodley, edits.

6) [APPENDIX A: EMAIL](#)

TOPS Community Panelists,

Thank you for participating in our June meeting. Edits to the summary report are due by July 28, 2023 and we need your help. We hope that you will add your comments directly to the Google document linked below. The panel summary does not require consensus and we encourage you to work together to create constructive guidance. The slack channel can be used to collaborate and, if meetings are needed, we are happy to help coordinate them. We will link the Panel Summary Report to a message on the slack channel.

Instructions:

1. Please provide your [ORCID](#) in the [update document](#) so that we may give credit for your participation in this [Google document](#).
2. We are asking for 3 volunteers - 1 for each Day. The Lead will synthesize responses and then work with the other leads to write the 'Recap' section in the appendices and make additions to the 'Key Findings' section in the main report or the [update document](#). Please put your name in the document in the section heading where it says '(Volunteer Name)' before making contributions to the main document. Be sure to add links to resources in the appendices.
3. The link to the Panel Summary report outline can be found [here](#) in the update document. We are looking for inputs on the BOCS (barriers, opportunities, change, sustain) or SWOT (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats) perceived in our current approach based on the three days outlined during the community panel.

We've provided resources to assist in your analysis – recordings, transcripts, and the slide decks. The Panel Summary outline includes suggestions for content and length.

What happens next:

It is important that you meet the 7/28 deadline to help inform decisions on future TOPS activities. We will upload the panel summary report to Zenodo, CC-BY license, and post to GitHub as part of the record of this meeting.

If you have any questions or are unable to participate in this editing and review process, please reach out to mglover.nasa@gmail.com and holly.e.norton@nasa.gov. Thanks for all the hard work and participation in the Transform to Open Science mission!

All the best,

The TOPS Team

7) APPENDIX B : DAILY RECAP

Day 1: TOPS Update and Creating the Curriculum

Wednesday June 14th, 2023		
Time (ET)	Agenda Item	Presenter
12:00 PM	Review of Agenda and Code of Conduct	Holly Norton
12:05 PM	Introductions	Chelle Gentemann
12:15 PM	Welcome	Kevin Murphy
12:30 PM	TOPS Update	Chelle Gentemann
1:00 PM	Year of Open Science	Jamaica Jones Chelle Gentemann
1:30 PM	Coffee Break	
1:45 PM	Open Science 101 Module Content Development	Diana Ly
2:45 PM	Coffee Break	
3:15 PM	Open Science 101 MOOC Development	Ilona Serrao
3:45 PM	Open Discussion	Holly Norton
4:10 PM	Wrap Up	Chelle Gentemann
4:15 PM	Day 1 of Panel Ends	

Day 2: Training 20K Scientists

Thursday June 15th, 2023		
Time (ET)	Agenda Item	Presenter
12:00 PM	Introduction and Review of Code of Conduct	Holly Norton
12:10 PM	Honoraria Q&A	NRESS
12:15 PM	TOPST Update	Steve Crawford
12:30 PM	Open Science 101 Certification	Diana Ly
12:45 PM	Open Science 101 Instructor training	Diana Ly
1:00 PM	Open Science 101 Rollout - Year 1 and Beyond	Paul Bremner
1:30 PM	Coffee Break	

1:45 PM	Community Forum (Public)	MSFC
2:45 PM	Coffee Break	
3:00 PM	Open Discussion	Holly Norton
3:25 PM	Wrap Up	Chelle Gentemann
3:30 PM	Day 2 of Panel Ends	

Day 3: Doubling Participation

<i>Friday June 16th, 2023</i>		
<i>Time (ET)</i>	<i>Agenda Item</i>	<i>Presenter</i>
12:00 PM	TOPS Recruitment and Outreach	Amanda Adams
12:30 PM	2024 Engagement Strategy	Amanda Adams Paul Bremner
1:00 PM	HQ DEIA Engagement Strategy	Malcolm Glover
1:30 PM	Coffee Break	
1:45 PM	SWOT Analysis Activity	Holly Norton
2:45 PM	Coffee Break	
3:15 PM	Open Discussion	Holly Norton
3:45 PM	Wrap Up	Chelle Gentemann
4:10 PM	Day 3 of Panel Ends	

8) APPENDIX C : RESOURCES

Below is a list of resources that were provided by panelists and participants during the three-day meeting.

Transform to Open Science (TOPS) GitHub Site

The [TOPS GitHub](#) site provides information on the TOPS mission and NASA's efforts to rapidly transform agencies, organizations, and communities to an inclusive culture of open science. TOPS is part of NASA's [Open-Source Science Initiative](#).

National Data Science Alliance (NDSA)

The [NDSA](#) is a national network of academic, industry, and government partnerships that will grow the capacity of Historically Black Colleges and Universities (HBCUs) to transform data science discoveries into tangible societal benefits. Follow this [link](#) to connect with NDSA via LinkedIn.

INCLUDES National Network

NSF's Eddie Bernice Johnson INCLUDES Initiative (Inclusion Across the Nation of Communities of Learners of Underrepresented Discoverers in Engineering and Science) is a comprehensive national initiative designed to enhance U.S. leadership in discoveries and innovations by focusing on diversity, inclusion and broadening participation in Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) at scale. NSF INCLUDES is one of the [NSF 10 Big Ideas](#).

Open Climate Campaign

The [Open Climate Campaign](#) is a multi-year campaign to promote open access to research to accelerate progress towards solving the climate crisis and preserving global biodiversity.

NASA Science Mission Directorate: Entrepreneurs Challenge

The [2023 NASA Entrepreneurs Challenge](#) seeks the development and commercialization of lunar payloads and climate science through an entrepreneurial and venture lens to advance the Agency's science exploration goals.

GitHub Tutorial - Beginner's Training Guide

A [tutorial on how to use GitHub](#) to create new repositories, clone repositories locally, commit changes and manage project files.

Version Control with Git

[Version Control with Git](#) is a lesson on keeping track of what you've done and to collaborate with other people. Every large software development project relies on it, and most programmers use it for their small jobs as well. And it isn't just for software: books, papers, small data sets, and anything that changes over time or needs to be shared can and should be stored in a version control system.

Open Grants

[Open Grants](#) is an open repository of funding proposals will elevate their recognition as scholarly products, improve access for the public and other grant seekers, and bring transparency to this facet of the research process. This site documents efforts toward this goal, including documentation of current planning activities and a prototype database.

Articles

[NASA Science Directorate Wants Help Prioritizing What Digital Resources It Should Open-Source First](#) by Aaron Boyd on Nextgov

[Why NASA and federal agencies are declaring this the Year of Open Science](#) by Chelle Gentemann on Nature